

JobED

Job with Education Report

School Education Report to Make Students Employable

Students of a government school in New Delhi cross high walls and barbed wires to abscond from the school. School education is bad and teachers have no control on students. Photo: Rakesh Raman / RMN News Service

स्कूल और कॉलेज की पढ़ाई है बेकार
इसीलिए तो पढ़े-लिखे भी हैं बेरोज़गार

An Editorial Initiative of Raman Media Network (RMN)

Author, Editor, Researcher: Rakesh Raman

January 2025

Table of Contents

JobEd

School Education Report to Make Students Employable

No.	Topic	Page
1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
2.	KEY FINDINGS OF THE REPORT	4
3.	STATUS OF EDUCATION AND UNEMPLOYMENT	5
4.	UNEMPLOYED YOUTH	7
5.	CURRENT EDUCATION SYSTEM	9
6.	FLAWED EDUCATION DELIVERY	14
7.	UNEMPLOYED DEGREE HOLDERS	15
8.	WEAK EDUCATION POLICY AND UNEMPLOYMENT	17
9.	PROBLEMS IN SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM	19
10.	EFFECTS OF POOR EDUCATION QUALITY IN SCHOOLS	19
11.	ADVERSE IMPACT OF POOR EDUCATION	19
12.	OVERVIEW OF THE NEW EDUCATION MODEL	21
13.	OBJECTIVES AND FEATURES OF NEW EDUCATION MODEL (CEF)	23
14.	STRUCTURE OF NEW EDUCATION MODEL (CEF)	24
15.	SUGGESTED STEPS TO IMPROVE EDUCATION IN SCHOOLS	30
16.	STEPS FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF NEW EDUCATION SYSTEM	32
17.	ABOUT THE AUTHOR (RAKESH RAMAN)	32
18.	CIRCULATION OF SCHOOL EDUCATION REPORT 2025	34

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

While the quality of school education continues to deteriorate in India, this research and consultative report provides an alternative model of school education. The report proposes to impart modern fundamental education and contemporary skills to school students so that they could be made employable in the current information-driven job market.

With emphasis on self-learning methodologies, the report advises parents, teachers, students, and policy-makers to revamp the current education system in schools and replace it with the job-oriented education models. It describes the irrelevance of the ongoing education with a number of examples which depict that even the top degree holders are not able to get jobs in the corporate sector because their education does not provide them necessary skills required in the private sector.

Flawed Education in Government and Private Schools

The report gives some examples of redundant syllabuses in schools and finds that the education is equally flawed in government as well as private schools of India.

While government jobs are scarce and degree holders are not employable in the corporate sector, unemployment is increasing rapidly in India. After getting higher education degrees, the job-seekers are ready to work at low-level jobs. Still, they are not able to get employed and face the atrocities of the government when they protest against increasing levels of unemployment.

The report also gives some examples of redundant syllabuses in schools and finds that the education is equally flawed in government as well as private schools of India. As the teachers are clueless about the evolving job requirements, they continue to teach students the obsolete subjects with archaic pedagogical techniques. The policy-makers have also not tried to develop education models that are directly linked to employment.

Likewise, with limited knowledge, parents are behaving with a herd mentality and satisfied with the obsolete education being imparted to their children.

The report proposes an alternative model of school education based on a dynamic Constructive Education Framework (CEF) developed by the report author Rakesh Raman. This alternative model works on the principle of “Learning for Earning” to make students employable and meet the larger objective of building a prosperous society in the country.

Alternative Education Model

The report proposes an alternative model of school education based on a dynamic Constructive Education Framework (CEF).

The report author Rakesh Raman is the government's national award winning journalist and founder of the humanitarian organization RMN Foundation in New Delhi. Among his editorial and social services, he runs multiple education awareness campaigns and writes academic and supplementary education books for children. He was also running a free school for deserving children to provide them modern education so that they could compete in the evolving job market.

He has also been running an online international education site “RMN Kids” for the past 12 years to provide the latest education-related information to students, parents, teachers, and other stakeholders in the education and employment areas.

Among other senior editorial and consulting positions, he had also been associated with the United Nations (UN) through the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) as a digital media expert to help businesses use technology for brand marketing and business development. His detailed profile is given below.

KEY FINDINGS OF THE REPORT

- The school education system continues to deteriorate in India.
- School students are being taught obsolete subjects with archaic pedagogical methods.

- School books are written haphazardly.
- The quality of school education is equally bad in government as well as private schools.
- The school teachers are not fully qualified to teach contemporary subjects.
- While teachers follow an ineffective book-to-board approach, they give burdensome homework and unnecessarily hold multiple exams throughout the year without contributing toward the academic development of students.
- The state as well as national education policies are so flawed that they fail to improve the quality of education.
- Since school education is not effective, the higher education in colleges and universities becomes meaningless.
- School education has no linkages with higher education and employment of students.
- Top degree holders are not able to get even lower-level jobs.
- Politicians tell blatant lies about the quality of education just to hoodwink the voters.
- After a strong primary education, the post-primary education should be based on specific subject streams.
- School education should have a direct link with the employability of students.
- The focus of education should be on self-learning techniques and hybrid skills which are required in the job market.
- Entrepreneurship training should form the core of the entire education lifecycle with the learning-for-earning principle.
- School education and higher education should be merged into a single institutional education model to make students employable sooner in their career paths.
- The entire education system should be made dynamic which has the flexibility to change the focus of learning based on job market requirements.

STATUS OF EDUCATION AND UNEMPLOYMENT

Since unemployment is increasing rapidly in India, there is an immediate need to design and develop a completely innovative system of education which has a direct correlation

with the employment prospects of students. The current education policies as well as the school education systems of the State and Central governments are running in an isolated manner without linking education with employment.

As schools persist with archaic syllabuses and obsolete pedagogical procedures, their education cannot make students employable. Also, higher education in colleges and universities is meaningless if the fundamental school education is flawed.

Unemployed Degree Holders

The population of so-called educated people or degree holders who are unemployed is increasing exponentially in the country.

That is why the population of so-called educated people or degree holders who are unemployed is increasing exponentially in the country. The model proposed in this report will provide proper education to school students with the aim to empower them to earn their livelihoods gracefully.

In the current education system, the degree holders are not getting jobs because their education is irrelevant and they are not employable in the modern business world. A recent 2024 report [reveals](#) that even the students of the premier Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) are not able to get jobs.

The IIT Delhi, for example, said in a Right to Information (RTI) reply that about 22% of its students who registered for placement between 2019 and 2023 could not secure a job. In a [report](#) of April 2024 published in *The Hindu* newspaper, it is said that the number of IIT students who could find employment in 2024 is about 40%. In other words, 60% of students fail to get a job even after their IIT education.

It is also [reported](#) that the average salaries for IIT graduates have remained stagnant with no raise in the past 4 years. Another [report](#) of April 7, 2024 in *The Economic Times* states that many IIT students grapple with a tough job market as they face placement challenges and lower remuneration. The situation is equally bad for all IITs and even for Indian Institutes of Management (IIMs). For example, reports [suggest](#) that IIT Bombay

faces 36% graduate unemployment soon after IIM Lucknow and BITS Pilani seek alumni help for placements.

The opposition political parties often blame the government of prime minister (PM) Narendra Modi for the job market crisis. However, the main reason for unemployment is the poor quality of education in Indian schools, colleges, and universities.

Obsolete Education

The education being imparted in all types of educational institutes is so irrelevant and obsolete that it is not required at all in any government or private organization.

The education being imparted in all types of educational institutes is so irrelevant and obsolete that it is not required at all in any government or private organization. That is why people with even higher education degrees of graduation or post-graduation remain jobless.

UNEMPLOYED YOUTH

The young people are the worst hit. A recent [research report](#) by the International Labour Organisation (ILO) and the Institute of Human Development (IHD) reveals that India's youth account for almost 83% of the unemployed workforce.

The [report](#) "*India Employment Report 2024: Youth employment, education and skills*" released in March 2024 adds that the share of youngsters with secondary or higher education in the total unemployed youth has almost doubled from 35.2% in 2000 to 65.7% in 2022.

Commenting on employment in India, the report says that it is dominated by poor-quality employment in the informal sector and informal employment. Also, employment in India is predominantly self-employment and casual employment.

According to the [report](#), nearly 82% of the workforce engages in the informal sector, and nearly 90% is informally employed. Due to the nature of employment growth since 2019,

the share of total employment, which is in the informal sector and/or in informal employment, increased.

The [report](#) further states that wages and earnings are stagnant or declining. While wages of casual labourers maintained a modest upward trend during 2012–22, real wages of regular workers either remained stagnant or declined.

Self-employed real earnings also declined after 2019. Overall, wages have remained low. As much as 62% of the unskilled casual agricultural workers and 70% of such workers in the construction sector at the all-India level did not receive the prescribed daily minimum wages in 2022, the report asserts.

The report argues that digitalization and introduction of new technologies are changing the structure of industrial employment. There has been a rapid introduction of digitally mediated gig and platform work, which is algorithmically controlled by the platforms that have brought about new features in control of the labour process.

Youth Unemployment

The ILO analysis shows that unemployment rates among youths showed a disturbing trend, increasing as the level of education rises, with the highest rates among youths with a graduate or technical training degree.

Increasingly, according to the report, platform and gig work have been expanding, but it is, to a large extent, the extension of informal work, with hardly any social security provisions. The ILO analysis shows that unemployment rates among youths showed a disturbing trend, increasing as the level of education rises, with the highest rates among youths with a graduate or technical training degree.

In particular, the concern is the disproportionately higher unemployment rate among youths with a technical degree or diploma, which has surpassed even the rate among youths with a general graduate degree.

What is even more alarming is that these rates consistently have been on the rise, the ILO report says, adding that unemployment rates among highly educated youths from

lower-income families are a particular cause for concern because they face equal or even higher unemployment rates than their counterparts from higher-income families.

Today, almost all educated students are not employable and most of them are not even trainable. School education is particularly responsible for the poor education standards at college and university levels. Since the fundamentals of education in schools are quite weak, students are not able to learn contemporary subjects in colleges and universities while there is a huge gap between the students' learning and the requirements of the job market.

CURRENT EDUCATION SYSTEM

At present, education in schools is so irrelevant that it is not required at all in any job market. After wasting at least 12 years in schools, the students are totally confused and not equipped for higher education needed for employment. The drudgery of education also causes mental retardation and a feeling of inferiority complex among the students. Since a lot of verbal garbage is stuffed into the burdensome syllabuses, the education also challenges the biological limits of students who are forced to blindly cram instead of understanding the relevant subjects.

Confused Students

After wasting at least 12 years in schools, the students are totally confused and not equipped for higher education needed for employment.

About 99% of students do not need to learn the prevailing subjects such as math, science, social science, and the obsolete computer applications. The others who want to take up professions related to these subjects are also not required to learn them like this because today's professions are driven by advanced computer applications and systems driven by artificial intelligence (AI) which generate this knowledge for the professionals working in these fields.

For example, no student is required to learn polynomials, triangles, and circles. Similarly, they can ignore the study of metals, rivers, geography, and the Russian revolution. If they

need any of this static knowledge in their jobs, they can get it instantly with a single click of mouse on their computers.

As the students, parents, teachers, and policy makers are not willing to change the redundant subjects, students are suffering as they are not getting jobs after studying those subjects. The employers in the contemporary era do not need job seekers who have studied any of these irrelevant topics in their schools or colleges.

Rather, they need workers who are fully skilled in modern areas of studies and who are trained to handle any work during their employment even if they have not learnt it during their years in schools and colleges.

Given below are some of the examples of the redundant subjects that are being taught in schools. Although the curriculum in all classes is totally useless, the following examples taken from NCERT [website](#) mainly cover classes 9-12 of schools.

The teachers are blindly teaching these redundant subjects and students are blindly studying these redundant subjects without realizing that these subjects cannot make them employable. An estimated 90% of students would never require the knowledge of these subjects throughout their lives. But they waste years on learning these subjects in schools. This time wastage of students can be avoided and this time can be utilized to provide the students relevant education and skills which are required by employers.

Some examples of redundant school education subjects are given below.

Examples of Redundant School Education Subjects

Meaningless education that scares students and challenges their biological limits of cramming needless expressions and formulas.

$$l = \pm \frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2 + c^2}}, m = \pm \frac{b}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2 + c^2}}, n = \pm \frac{c}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2 + c^2}}$$

where, depending on the desired sign of k , either a positive or a negative sign is to be taken for l, m and n .

For any line, if a, b, c are direction ratios of a line, then $ka, kb, kc; k \neq 0$ is also a set of direction ratios. So, any two sets of direction ratios of a line are also proportional. Also, for any line there are infinitely many sets of direction ratios.

11.2.1 Relation between the direction cosines of a line

Consider a line RS with direction cosines l, m, n . Through the origin draw a line parallel to the given line and take a point $P(x, y, z)$ on this line. From P draw a perpendicular PA on the x -axis (Fig. 11.2).

Let $OP = r$. Then $\cos \alpha = \frac{OA}{OP} = \frac{x}{r}$. This gives $x = lr$.

Similarly, $y = mr$ and $z = nr$

Thus $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = r^2 (l^2 + m^2 + n^2)$

Example 12 Find intervals in which the function given by $f(x) = \sin 3x$, $x \in \left[0, \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$ is (a) increasing (b) decreasing.

Solution We have

$$f(x) = \sin 3x$$

$$\text{or } f'(x) = 3\cos 3x$$

Therefore, $f'(x) = 0$ gives $\cos 3x = 0$ which in turn gives $3x = \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{3\pi}{2}$ (as $x \in \left[0, \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$) implies $3x \in \left[0, \frac{3\pi}{2}\right]$. So $x = \frac{\pi}{6}$ and $\frac{\pi}{2}$. The point $x = \frac{\pi}{6}$ divides the interval $\left[0, \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$ into two disjoint intervals $\left[0, \frac{\pi}{6}\right]$ and $\left(\frac{\pi}{6}, \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$.

Fig 6.5

Now, $f'(x) > 0$ for all $x \in \left[0, \frac{\pi}{6}\right]$ as $0 \leq x < \frac{\pi}{6} \Rightarrow 0 \leq 3x < \frac{\pi}{2}$ and $f'(x) < 0$ for all $x \in \left(\frac{\pi}{6}, \frac{\pi}{2}\right]$ as $\frac{\pi}{6} < x < \frac{\pi}{2} \Rightarrow \frac{\pi}{2} < 3x < \frac{3\pi}{2}$.

2nd Series										
	Y	Zr	Nb	Mo	Tc	Ru	Rh	Pd	Ag	Cd
Z	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48
5s	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	2
4d	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	10	10	10

3rd Series										
	La	Hf	Ta	W	Re	Os	Ir	Pt	Au	Hg
Z	57	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80
6s	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2
5d	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	9	10	10

4th Series										
	Ac	Rf	Db	Sg	Bh	Hs	Mt	Ds	Rg	Cn
Z	89	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112
7s	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2
6d	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	10	10

The electronic configurations of outer orbitals of Zn, Cd, Hg and Cn are represented by the general formula $(n-1)d^{10}ns^2$. The orbitals in these elements are completely filled in the ground state as well as in their common oxidation states. Therefore, they are not regarded as transition elements.

discussed in detail in Chapter 9 on the basis of rectilinear propagation of light. Here we just describe the behaviour of the wavefronts as they undergo reflection or refraction. In Fig. 10.7(a) we consider a plane wave passing through a thin prism. Clearly, since the speed of light waves is less in glass, the lower portion of the incoming wavefront (which travels through the greatest thickness of glass) will get delayed resulting in a tilt in the emerging wavefront as shown in the figure. In Fig. 10.7(b) we consider a plane wave incident on a thin convex lens; the central part of the incident plane wave traverses the thickest portion of the lens and is delayed the most. The emerging wavefront has a depression at the centre and therefore the wavefront becomes spherical and converges to the point F which is known as the focus. In Fig. 10.7(c) a plane wave is incident on a concave mirror and on reflection we have a spherical wave converging to the focal point F. In a similar manner, we can understand refraction and reflection by concave lenses and convex mirrors.

FIGURE 10.7 Refraction of a plane wave by (a) a thin prism. (b) a convex lens. (c) Reflection of a plane wave by a concave mirror.

Definition 2 A parabola is the set of all points in a plane that are equidistant from a fixed line and a fixed point (not on the line) in the plane.

The fixed line is called the *directrix* of the parabola and the fixed point F is called the *focus* (Fig 11.13). ('Para' means 'for' and 'bola' means 'throwing', i.e., the shape described when you throw a ball in the air).

Note If the fixed point lies on the fixed line, then the set of points in the plane, which are equidistant from the fixed point and the fixed line is the straight line through the fixed point and perpendicular to the fixed line. We call this straight line as *degenerate case* of the parabola.

A line through the focus and perpendicular to the *directrix* is called the *axis* of the parabola. The point of intersection of parabola with the axis is called the *vertex* of the parabola (Fig 11.14).

Fig 11.13

272 MATHEMATICS

Therefore $AQ^2 = AN^2 + NQ^2$... (2)

From (1) and (2), we have

$$PQ^2 = PA^2 + AN^2 + NQ^2$$

Now $PA = y_2 - y_1$, $AN = x_2 - x_1$ and $NQ = z_2 - z_1$

Hence $PQ^2 = (x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2$

Therefore $PQ = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2}$

This gives us the distance between two points (x_1, y_1, z_1) and (x_2, y_2, z_2) .

In particular, if $x_1 = y_1 = z_1 = 0$, i.e., point P is origin O, then $OQ = \sqrt{x_2^2 + y_2^2 + z_2^2}$, which gives the distance between the origin O and any point Q (x_2, y_2, z_2) .

Example 3 Find the distance between the points P(1, -3, 4) and Q(-4, 1, 2).

Solution The distance PQ between the points P(1, -3, 4) and Q(-4, 1, 2) is

$$PQ = \sqrt{(-4-1)^2 + (1+3)^2 + (2-4)^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{25 + 16 + 4}$$

$$= \sqrt{45} = 3\sqrt{5} \text{ units}$$

Examples of Redundant School Education Subjects

Meaningless education that scares students and challenges their biological limits of cramming needless expressions and formulas.

Let us consider the ozone molecule (O_3). The Lewis structure of O_3 may be drawn as:

The atoms have been numbered as 1, 2 and 3. The formal charge on:

- The central O atom marked 1

$$= 6 - 2 - \frac{1}{2}(6) = +1$$

- The end O atom marked 2

$$= 6 - 4 - \frac{1}{2}(4) = 0$$

- The end O atom marked 3

$$= 6 - 6 - \frac{1}{2}(2) = -1$$

Hence, we represent O_3 along with the formal charges as follows:

So, the octet rule of most of the organic compounds and it applies mainly to the second period elements of the periodic table. There are three types of exceptions to the octet rule.

The incomplete octet of the central atom
In some compounds, the number of electrons surrounding the central atom is less than eight. This is especially the case with elements having less than four valence electrons. Examples are $LiCl$, BeH_2 and BCl_3 .

Li , Be and B have 1, 2 and 3 valence electrons only. Some other such compounds are $AlCl_3$ and BF_3 .

Odd-electron molecules

In molecules with an odd number of electrons like nitric oxide, NO and nitrogen dioxide, NO_2 , the octet rule is not satisfied for all the atoms.

The expanded octet

Elements in and beyond the third period of the periodic table have, apart from 3s and 3p orbitals, 3d orbitals also available for bonding.

280

PHYSICS

Fig. 11.2 Pressure versus temperature of a low density gas kept at constant volume.

Fig. 11.3 A plot of pressure versus temperature and extrapolation of lines for low density gases indicates the same absolute zero temperature.

relationship. Notice that since $PV = \text{constant}$ and $V/T = \text{constant}$ for a given quantity of gas, then PV/T should also be a constant. This relationship is known as ideal gas law. It can be written in a more general form that applies not just to a given quantity of a single gas but to any quantity of any low-density gas and is known as **ideal-gas equation**:

$$\frac{PV}{T} = \mu R \quad \text{or} \quad PV = \mu RT \quad (11.2)$$

where, μ is the number of moles in the sample of gas and R is called universal gas constant:

named after the British scientist Lord Kelvin. On this scale, -273.15°C is taken as the zero point, that is 0 K (Fig. 11.4).

158

MATHEMATICS

Let us now find the distance between any two points $P(x_1, y_1)$ and $Q(x_2, y_2)$. Draw PR and QS perpendicular to the x -axis. A perpendicular from the point P on QS is drawn to meet it at the point T (see Fig. 7.5).

Then, $OR = x_1$, $OS = x_2$. So, $RS = x_2 - x_1 = PT$. Also, $SQ = y_2$, $ST = PR = y_1$. So, $QT = y_2 - y_1$.

Now, applying the Pythagoras theorem in ΔPTQ , we get

$$PQ^2 = PT^2 + QT^2$$

$$= (x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2$$

Therefore, $PQ = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2}$

Note that since distance is always non-negative, we take only the positive square root. So, the distance between the points $P(x_1, y_1)$ and $Q(x_2, y_2)$ is

$$PQ = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2},$$

which is called the **distance formula**.

Fig. 7.5

Now, using Pythagoras theorem,

$$BC = \sqrt{AB^2 - AC^2}$$

and

$$QR = \sqrt{PQ^2 - PR^2}$$

$$\text{So, } \frac{BC}{QR} = \frac{\sqrt{AB^2 - AC^2}}{\sqrt{PQ^2 - PR^2}} = \frac{\sqrt{k^2PQ^2 - k^2PR^2}}{\sqrt{PQ^2 - PR^2}} = \frac{k\sqrt{PQ^2 - PR^2}}{\sqrt{PQ^2 - PR^2}} = k \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2), we have

$$\frac{AC}{PR} = \frac{AB}{PQ} = \frac{BC}{QR}$$

Then, by using Theorem 6.4, $\Delta ACB \sim \Delta PRQ$ and therefore, $\angle B = \angle Q$.

Example 3: Consider ΔACB , right-angled at C , in which $AB = 29$ units, $BC = 21$ units and $\angle ABC = \theta$ (see Fig. 8.10). Determine the values of

- $\cos^2 \theta + \sin^2 \theta$,
- $\cos^2 \theta - \sin^2 \theta$.

Solution: In ΔACB , we have

$$AC = \sqrt{AB^2 - BC^2} = \sqrt{(29)^2 - (21)^2}$$

$$= \sqrt{(29 - 21)(29 + 21)} = \sqrt{(8)(50)} = \sqrt{400} = 20 \text{ units}$$

Fig. 8.10

Figure 7.2 Reflex arc

Figure 1.8 (b) Iron nails and copper sulphate solutions compared before and after the experiment

Why does the iron nail become brownish in colour and the blue colour of copper sulphate solution fades?

The following chemical reaction takes place in this Activity—

In this reaction, iron has displaced or removed another element, copper, from copper sulphate solution. This reaction is known as displacement reaction.

Other examples of displacement reactions are

Zinc and lead are more reactive elements than copper. They displace copper from its compounds.

Examples of Redundant School Education Subjects

Obsolete education that has no relevance in the contemporary job market.

1.3 The Coming of Socialism to Europe

Perhaps one of the most far-reaching visions of how society should be structured was socialism. By the mid - nineteenth century in Europe, socialism was a well-known body of ideas that attracted widespread attention.

Socialists were against private property, and saw it as the root of all social ills of the time. Why? Individuals owned the property that gave employment but the proprietors were concerned only with personal gain and not with the welfare of those who made the property productive. So if society as a whole rather than single individuals controlled property, more attention would be paid to collective social interests. Socialists wanted this change and campaigned for it.

How could a society without property operate? What would be the basis of socialist society?

Socialists had different visions of the future. Some believed in the idea of cooperatives. Robert Owen (1771-1858), a leading English manufacturer, sought to build a cooperative community called New Harmony in Indiana (USA). Other socialists felt that cooperatives could not be built on a wide

EXERCISE

- Choose the right answer from the four alternatives given below.
 - The Tropic of Cancer does not pass through
 - Rajasthan
 - Odisha
 - Chhattisgarh
 - Tripura
 - The easternmost longitude of India is
 - 87° 25' E
 - 68° 7' E
 - 77° 6' E
 - 82° 32' E
 - Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, West Bengal and Sikkim have common frontiers with
 - China
 - Bhutan
 - Nepal
 - Myanmar
 - If you intend to visit Kavarati during your summer vacations, which one of the following Union Territories of India you will be going to
 - Puducherry
 - Lakshadweep
 - Andaman and Nicobar
 - Daman and Diu
 - My friend hails from a country which does not share land boundary with India. Identify the country.
 - Bhutan
 - Tajikistan
 - Bangladesh
 - Nepal
- Answer the following questions briefly.
 - Name the group of islands lying in the Arabian Sea.
 - Name the countries which are larger than India.
 - Which island group of India lies to its south-east?
 - Which island countries are our southern neighbours?
- The sun rises two hours earlier in Arunachal Pradesh as compared to Gujarat in the west but the watches show the same time. How does this happen?
- The central location of India at the head of the Indian Ocean is considered of great significance. Why?

Let alone students, even teachers can't learn all these subjects by heart to clear the exams. The education based on these complex subjects was imparted to students when there was no artificial intelligence (AI) and instant knowledge-gaining tools like ChatGPT. In fact, ChatGPT (or Generative Pre-trained Transformer) is an artificial intelligence or AI-based online tool called chatbot which generates human-like text responses to prompts or user queries. It was launched by OpenAI in November 2022.

Now, there is a surfeit of such AI tools that school students can use if they require the knowledge of any subject being taught in schools. Therefore, instead of wasting their time on these complex subjects, students can devote their time on learning job-related skills which are currently not being taught in schools.

Obviously, there is a need to revamp the directionless school education system in India so that students can acquire new skills that can help them progress in the modern information-driven world. The Central government and the State governments of India have not taken any steps in the past many decades to modernize the archaic system that is not producing an employable workforce.

Similarly, teachers and parents are so ignorant about the requirements of the ever-evolving job market that they do not feel the need to design relevant courses and new teaching methodologies to empower students to earn their livelihoods. As a result, joblessness is spreading like a deadly disease in India and the unemployed students have become a veritable timebomb which can explode under increasing distress and cause serious civil unrest in the country.

FLAWED EDUCATION DELIVERY

It is a known fact that the entire school education delivery mechanism across the country is totally flawed. Since the fundamental school education is fragile, the college and university education becomes meaningless. As a result, even the educated are treated as uneducated in the job market.

This harsh reality is reflected in the global human development index (HDI) which indicates the level of schooling, education, skills, and life expectancy in a country. As the HDI position of India staggers at a dismal [rank](#) of 134 in 193 countries, there is hardly any workforce in the country that is employable in any professional job.

Competition in Job Market

Almost all school students even after completing their schooling along with tuitions remain illiterate who cannot be trained further to compete in the current job market.

As the predicament persists, politicians of all political parties are telling lies about the quality of school education which is constantly deteriorating across the country. An unprecedented hype is being created around school education by the governments while the governments have done nothing to save the decaying education systems.

There is no attempt to revamp the syllabuses and books of students and the quality of school teachers is so bad that they are not even trainable. Government is wasting huge money on training teachers who cannot be trained to produce an employable workforce. Instead of learning and teaching properly in the schools, teachers are promoting an illegal trade in the form of private tuitions. Almost all school students even after

completing their schooling along with tuitions remain illiterate who cannot be trained further to compete in the current job market.

Since school education is totally directionless, college education cannot make students employable. Students who cannot get admission in colleges opt for informal education through options such as expensive private colleges or School of Open Learning (SOL). But this informal route of private education or SOL is a big deception which cannot provide necessary education and skills to students. Only rejected students opt for private colleges and SOL and waste their time in this useless method of learning which cannot get them proper jobs.

Since parents are clueless about the education necessities, they are being cheated by politicians for electoral advantages. After spending 12 years on school education, students realize that they have wasted all that time of their life. At that time, all the career avenues are closed for them. Thus, parents are the worst enemies of their children who are accepting bad education instead of demanding good education from the government.

The bad quality of school education has its repercussions. Today, for example, out of nearly 500 million workers in India, over 94% work in the unorganized sector as pushcart vendors, street hawkers, domestic servants, delivery workers, and so on. This means the education standards in India are so irrelevant that they are not producing a workforce employable for respectable jobs in the organized enterprises. Even people with top education degrees do not get proper jobs.

UNEMPLOYED DEGREE HOLDERS

As students, parents, teachers, and policy makers are not willing to change the obsolete syllabuses and old pedagogical methods, students are suffering as they are not getting jobs. The employers do not need job seekers who have studied any of these irrelevant topics in their schools or colleges. Although degree holders keep protesting on roads to get jobs, actually they are not employable.

Some recent media reports of the cruel reality of educated unemployed are given below.

Media Reports of the Cruel Reality of Educated Unemployed Courtesy: Respective Media Publications

संगरूर में प्रदर्शन • सीएम निवास तक जाने से रोकने को पुलिस ने खड़ी की बैरिकेड की दीवार रोजगार मांगने पहुंचे टेट पास बेरोजगारों को पुलिस ने मारी लाठियां, 3 बेहोश, 2 घायल

19 जुलाई को शिक्षा मंत्री से बैठक के आयोजन के बाद युनिवर्स के सदस्यों ने खत्म किया धरना

आरोप : रोजगार तो दूर की बात सीएम मिलने का भी समय नहीं दे रहे

मकसद न्याय। होकार

रोजगार को प्राप्त करने के लिए बेरोजगार छात्रों का निवास के समक्ष बेरोजगारों के टेट पास अडवाक युनिवर्स के सदस्यों और पुलिस में खड़ी हुई। युनिवर्स के सदस्यों द्वारा निवास के समक्ष टेट पास अडवाक युनिवर्स के सदस्यों को रोकने के लिए बैरिकेड की दीवार खड़ी कर पुलिस सदस्यों को गैर कानूनिक गतिविधियों में शामिल करने के लिए कहा गया। युनिवर्स के सदस्यों ने पुलिस के सदस्यों को रोकने के लिए बैरिकेड की दीवार खड़ी कर पुलिस सदस्यों को गैर कानूनिक गतिविधियों में शामिल करने के लिए कहा गया। युनिवर्स के सदस्यों ने पुलिस के सदस्यों को रोकने के लिए बैरिकेड की दीवार खड़ी कर पुलिस सदस्यों को गैर कानूनिक गतिविधियों में शामिल करने के लिए कहा गया।

9 हजार भरविद्ये का रिग्रामन निगमो संसकरो... 4161 पदों में से 1300 पदों को भर्ती कर दिया गया है।

युनिवर्स की मुख्य मांग... 4161 पदों में से 1300 पदों को भर्ती कर दिया गया है।

इसमें, पंजाब में रोजगार का 2 धंधे घघका जाम, 19 से रभी सपुके रोकने की चेदार्नी... 4161 पदों में से 1300 पदों को भर्ती कर दिया गया है।

Around 27,000 Haryana youth including engineers and graduates applied for 13 vacant posts for Peon in Haryana. [[Video Link](#)]

707 पोस्ट पर 7.5 लाख दावेदार, MBA-MCA वाले भी मोची, माली, धोबी बनने की रेस में

Vishal.Sharma3@timesgroup.com

दिल्ली पुलिस में जांब के लिए हो रही लिखित परीक्षाएं

पेपर लीक के शक में दो सब इंस्पेक्टर सरपेड

दिल्ली पुलिस में जांब के लिए हो रही लिखित परीक्षाएं... 707 पोस्टों पर 7.5 लाख दावेदार... 1300 पदों में से 1300 पदों को भर्ती कर दिया गया है।

NATIONAL HERALD | नवजीवन

Home Nation States 360° World Business Environment Culture + Cinema Sports

INDIA
Engineers, doctors, post graduates take up jobs of peons and bailiffs in Gujarat HC
Joblessness compels hundreds of highly qualified candidates to accept lowly paid jobs in Gujarat

October 9, 2019 media report [[Link](#)]

NDTV | LIVE TV | LATEST | ELECTIONS | INDIA | WORLD | CITIES | EDUCATION | OPINION | VIDEOS | AUTO

News > India News > Video: Railing Collapses As 1,800 Aspirants Turn Up For 10 Jobs In Gujarat

Video: Railing Collapses As 1,800 Aspirants Turn Up For 10 Jobs In Gujarat

While the Congress has hit out at the BJP, an MP from the ruling party has shifted the blame onto the company which organised the open interview.

July 11, 2024 media report [[Link](#)]

THE ECONOMIC TIMES | Politics

Home | ETime | Markets | Market Data | News | Industry | Dip Politics | Wealth | MF | Tech | Careers | Opinion | NDI | Panache | Luxury | Videos

News Flash > Devendra Fadnis named as Maharashtra CM at BJP core committee meeting

Over 93,000 candidates, including 3,700 PhD holders apply for peon job in UP

August 30, 2018 media report [[Link](#)]

NDTV | LIVE TV | LATEST | ELECTIONS | INDIA | WORLD | CITIES | EDUCATION | OPINION | VIDEOS | AUTO

News > India News > Engineers, Postgraduates Line Up For Peon Jobs In Chhattisgarh

Engineers, Postgraduates Line Up For Peon Jobs In Chhattisgarh

There were long queues outside 657 examination centres in Raipur as 2.25 lakh candidates had applied for only 91 vacant peon posts

September 25, 2022 media report [[Link](#)]

Engineers line up for 'cycle test' to become peons in Kerala

T C Sreemol / TNN / Updated: Oct 28, 2023, 06:52 IST

Scores of BTech holders and graduates in Kerala's Ernakulam queued up to apply for a government office peon job, despite requiring only a Class 7 qualification and the ability to ride a bicycle. The job offers a monthly salary of around Rs 23,000 and is seen as more secure than gig economy jobs. The cycling test is still a requirement, although it serves no practical purpose, and 101 candidates have cleared the test and now face an endurance test.

Read Less

KOCHI: The qualification sought was Class 7-pass, plus the ability to ride a bicycle. Yet, early on Friday in Kerala's Ernakulam, scores of BTech

October 28, 2023 media report [[Link](#)]

As stated above, today employers need professionals who are perfectly skilled in modern areas of enterprise work and who are trained to handle any task during their employment even if they have not learnt it in schools and colleges.

Instead of asking the governments to revamp their education systems to make them employable, students demand jobs while they do not possess any education or skills to work in any corporate or government environment. When such unemployable students demand jobs after completing their education, the governments reject their demands and use brutal force to crush their protests in different states of India.

Moreover, the web is replete with facts and figures that [reveal](#) the bottlenecks in the job market and the irrelevance of Indian education systems which cannot produce a workforce for the emerging fields of economic activity.

WEAK EDUCATION POLICY AND IMPACT OF UNEMPLOYMENT

While a national education policy was released in 1986, the current education system with this policy in India is based on archaic syllabuses and obsolete pedagogy which cannot make students employable in the cut-throat job market. The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) is so crude and complex that it cannot be implemented.

Therefore, there is no serious attempt by any State government to implement the recommendations of the new education policy, as it is a smorgasbord of carelessly lifted ideas that cannot resuscitate the decayed education system - particularly the school education system. Many Indian states have flatly [refused](#) to implement the NEP 2020 because it is as bad as the previous education policies.

As a result, the joblessness is spreading like a pandemic disease and the students taught under this stale system cannot be called educated, as they never get ready for any work that can give them proper employment. Students come to know about the futility of their education when they get degrees after completing their courses but those degrees cannot get them jobs.

At this stage of hopelessness, a large number of students go into a state of depression and lose interest in their lives. Now, a number of educated unemployed people have

started committing suicides. According to the latest [data](#), the year 2020 saw the highest number of suicides among the unemployed in India. The National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) data quoted in Rajya Sabha on February 9, 2022 by an Indian minister reveals that 3,548 people died by suicide due to unemployment in 2020.

According to the NCRB data, the highest number of suicides due to unemployment in 2020 was reported from Karnataka (720), followed by Maharashtra (625), Tamil Nadu (336), Assam (234), and Uttar Pradesh (227). A [report](#) of February 10, 2022 in *The Indian Express* says that suicides due to unemployment have been increasing over the past few years – the toll was 2,851 in 2019; 2,741 in 2018; 2,404 in 2017; 2,298 in 2016; 2,723 in 2015; and 2,207 in 2014. The report adds that the total number of suicides among the unemployed during the current BJP-led government in India (2014-2020) was 18,772, an average of 2,681 deaths per year.

Government Inaction

Despite the persisting problem, the governments in different states of India are not willing to carry out education reforms and blindly (or perhaps deliberately) use the obsolete school education and pedagogical models.

Despite the persisting problem, the governments in different states of India are not willing to carry out education reforms and blindly (or perhaps deliberately) use the obsolete school education and pedagogical models. Therefore, they fail to produce students who are ready to pursue meaningful higher education required for the emerging job market in which the workers are supposed to possess hybrid skills.

Indian politicians - most of whom are history-sheeters with serious criminal records - do not want to improve the education systems to empower people because properly educated voters will stop voting for them. Now, most politicians and political parties win elections with the votes of totally uneducated citizens who can be deceived with false promises and misleading advertisements. Instead of empowering citizens with the right education so that they could earn their livelihoods with dignity, politicians are making them survive on government dole and thus building a dependent society which is destined to ruin the country.

As there is no accountability for teachers, bureaucrats, and politicians who are working carelessly to waste huge public money, the education standards of schools continue to be in the doldrums.

PROBLEMS IN THE CURRENT SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

- No relationship between education and employability of students
- Incompetent teachers who do not understand the evolving pedagogy
- Careless and ignorant bureaucrats in the education departments
- Exaggerated hype by naive politicians with a focus on votes
- No Return on Investment (RoI) analysis for expenditure on education
- No method to assess the quality of education and learning outcomes

EFFECTS OF POOR EDUCATION QUALITY IN SCHOOLS

- Spoiling the lives and careers of millions of children
- Increasing joblessness resulting in social unrest
- Increasing crimes in schools and other parts of the country
- Increasing drug addiction among students
- Wastage of huge public money
- Creation of dependent, idle society which survives only on government dole

ADVERSE IMPACT OF POOR EDUCATION ON STUDENTS

Since parents, teachers, bureaucrats, and politicians are not aware of the modern education paradigms, they are spoiling the lives and careers of students with useless education that has no link with employability. Students keep attending school classes like a herd but never question the system which is full of flaws. In this rigmarole, students waste plenty of their time in school education which can never help them develop their careers. The situation is equally bad in government as well as private schools.

It is estimated that in a typical 12 years of schooling, a student wastes approximately 65% of their time on learning subjects that are not relevant. More than 95% of school students, for example, do not need to learn existing subjects such as mathematics, science, history,

geography, etc. which have no relevance in the contemporary world. A subject is useless if it has no direct connectivity with a student's career.

All the students need not learn all the subjects. As an analogy, a swimmer need not learn the game of badminton or a cobbler does not need to learn horse riding. Likewise, mathematics or science subjects are only for those who want to pursue careers in the field of science.

Then they need not learn about Russian and French Revolutions which are being taught to them unnecessarily. Similarly, if a student has to become a marketing manager in a consumer products company, they need not waste time on polynomials and quadratic equations or chemical reactions and magnetic effects, which are being taught in schools without any purpose. The entire school education should be focused on the job that the student intends to do.

Impact on Health

All this burdensome education takes its toll on students' health, and in the absence of physical activity many students lose their cognitive ability and face physical and mental challenges.

The time wastage also happens when a student spends on average 8 hours daily in school and then repeats the same futile education in their home to complete the exercises given by the teachers. Some students even attend private tuitions after coming back from their schools.

All this burdensome education takes its toll on students' health, and in the absence of physical activity many students lose their cognitive ability and face physical and mental challenges. This is one of the main reasons for students to drop out from schools.

Although the governments have no system to measure the impact of painful education on school students, it is believed that nearly 80% - or 8 in every 10 - school students are suffering from multiple ailments - such as headaches, mental stress, poor vision, anxiety, and depression - that aggravate when they grow older. Obviously, there is an immediate need to save school students from this torturous education which is more harmful than

helpful to them. The problem can be solved by providing focused education, linking the subjects with potential jobs.

OVERVIEW OF THE NEW EDUCATION MODEL

The new proposed school education model is supposed to enhance the employability of students in the current as well as future job market. It will also empower the students to acquire self-learning skills which are required to gain employment in the future enterprise domains.

Subjects in Primary Education for the First 5 Years of Schooling

In the revamped model, education needs to be categorized in different streams. After the fundamental education in the primary school, the syllabuses should be customized for different groups of students. The objective is to help students focus only on those

subjects that are relevant for them in getting jobs. The teachers will also get trained to impart education according to the new system.

The primary education for the first 5 years of schooling should include foundational subjects such as Arithmetic, English, Information Technology (IT), Moral Education, and a local language (such as Hindi, Punjabi, Gujarati, Marathi, etc.).

Higher Education Streams

The higher education from 6th to 12th year of schooling should be divided into 4 different streams: Humanities, STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math), Commerce or Trade, and Specialized Domains such as Environment, Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Human Rights, Governance, and so on.

The total education period for each student will be 14 years (12 years of classroom education and 2 years of on-the-job training). After successfully completing the 14 years of education, a student will be fully employable in the area for which they have been

trained. With this specialized education model, you can do away with college and university education which will become redundant.

Constructive Education Framework

It is an innovative education model developed to impart modern education to students and it connects education with employability so that students could get jobs in the market.

The schools are urged to implement the **Constructive Education Framework** (CEF), which is an innovative education model developed to impart modern education to students.

OBJECTIVES OF NEW EDUCATION MODEL (CEF)

- To connect education with employability
- To focus on skills development rather than on plain theory
- To teach students the hybrid job skills required in the future job markets
- To teach with the principle of “Learning for Earning”
- To produce morally sound and honest people
- To build a clean and prosperous society
- To achieve economic growth in the country

FEATURES OF NEW EDUCATION MODEL (CEF)

- Technology including Artificial Intelligence (AI) integration for the entire learning lifecycle
- Use of advanced English language with focus on language application
- Coverage of relevant subjects to meet the always-changing job market demand
- Modular form of education
- Focus on reading, writing, speaking, debating, and problem solving
- Self-learning form of education
- Promotion of creativity among the students covering different fields of human activity

STRUCTURE OF NEW EDUCATION MODEL (CEF)

Education Phases

Initial Phase

Humanities / Arts / Management (Total 12 years of education)

Next Phase

STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math) when requisite resources are available

Target Age Group of Students

Target Age Group of Students for Admission: 4 – 15 years

Younger students will undergo the entire education program

Others will learn part of the program depending on their age and aptitude

Education Module I

Age: 4 – 7 years or first 3 years (1 – 3) of education

(Six periods a day; Each period of 45-minute duration)

Subjects – 6

1. Languages (Hindi and English)

Reading, writing, speaking, listening, and discussion.

Focus on the application of language to produce usable content

2. Arithmetic / Business Stats

Numerical calculations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. Essential components of business statistics such as percentage calculation, compound annual growth rate (CAGR) calculation, different statistical charts, etc.

3. Creative

Activities such as graphic design, painting, music, acting, gardening, photography, etc. with computer applications

4. Entertainment

Didactic entertainment with stories, movies, and animation

5. Lifestyle

Daily routine including health care, exercise, dress, cleanliness, behavioral and moral education, discipline, time management, etc.

6. Sports

Indoor and outdoor games based on a child's interest

Education Module II

Age: 8 – 10 years or next 3 years (4 – 6) of education

(Eight periods a day; Each period of 45-minute duration)

Continuation of Module I

Additional Subjects (Two additional periods)

1. Information Technology

Fundamentals of computers and communications

2. Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP)

Basic financial management, commerce, economics, marketing & sales, and introduction to ERP

Education Module III

Age: 11 – 13 years or next 3 years (7- 9) of education

(Eight periods a day; Each period of 45-minute duration)

1. Information Technology Applications

Theory and practical knowledge of specific tech products and services in relation to the market demand

2. Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP)

Advanced coverage of each ERP module or business processes such as Human Resource Management (HRM), Production Planning and Control, Financial Management, Cost Management, Purchase, Quality Control, Sales & Marketing, Supply Chain Management (SCM), Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Vendor Risk Management (VRM), and so on.

3. Current Affairs

Study, observation, understanding, opinion, expression, and content creation on local and global issues such as environment, rights, conflicts, poverty, and so on.

4. Use of Public Services

General awareness about public services such as post offices, banks, transport, e-governance services, etc. and how to use them. Will include social interactions, human values, and business etiquette.

5. Political Systems

Local and international political systems with their features

6. International Trade

International trade practices, business norms, demand / supply management

7. Entertainment

Quality of entertainment with global perspective and career orientation for students

8. Sports

Recreation and professional sports education

Education Module IV

Age: 14 – 16 years or next 3 years (10 – 12) of education

Ten hours of education every day (flexible time for each period)

After the first nine years of education as described above, it will be clear on which career stream a student should go. In this Module, each student will be provided a customized education to help them gain requisite skills in a particular professional area.

Professional Areas

Financial Management

Human Resource Management (HRM)

Sales & Marketing

Marketing Communications

Mass Communications

Commerce and Trade

Agriculture and Farming

Digital Media Management

Research & Analysis

Law and Human Rights

Creative (acting, graphics, dance, music, filmmaking)

Democracy and Governance

Employability and Career

After successfully completing the 12 years of education in the current phase covering Management Studies, students can either become part of a subsistence-based “**Enterprise Clustering Model**” or can get a respectable job in the open market.

In the “Enterprise Clustering Model,” students will create and manage their own enterprises in collaboration with established enterprises.

Top Corporate and Government Positions

After completing the education as prescribed in CEF, students can take top corporate positions such as:

Chief Marketing Officers

Chief Financial Officers

Customer Service Managers

Business Process Managers

Economists

AI Prompt Engineers

Political Analysts

Journalists / Editors / Writers

Digital Media Managers

Chief Executive Officers

Teachers

Advocates

Honest Politicians

Citizen Service Managers

Entrepreneurs

Some students can also join creative fields like acting, painting, music, filmmaking, etc.

Business Streams Under Enterprise Clustering Model

Multimedia Content Marketing

Handicraft Products Manufacturing

Contact Centers / Business Process Outsourcing (BPO)

Sales & Marketing (Outsourcing model)

Agricultural Marketing

Research and Analysis

Apparel Design

Creative Books Production

Brand Management Agency

Others

The business streams under “**Enterprise Clustering Model**” can employ hundreds of thousands (lakhs) of people.

Career Support to Students

- On-the-job training for students in companies and government departments
- Collaboration with corporate sector to get employment for students
- Government / private certification of students’ skills
- Career counselling
- Placement support in India and abroad

The State governments can implement the new system as a pilot project, initially comprising about 10 schools in each state. Subsequently, it can be replicated in more schools in the states. The implementation will include the training of a select group of teachers who will teach according to the new education model in each school.

Implementation of New Education System

The implementation of the new system will include the training of a select group of teachers who will teach according to the new education model in each school.

SUGGESTED STEPS TO IMPROVE EDUCATION IN SCHOOLS

In order to save school education and school children from the directionless ongoing system, a number of remedial steps should be taken. Some of them are listed below.

Appointment of Qualified Teachers: Since most existing school teachers are neither qualified nor trainable in the contemporary fields of studies, they must be replaced with new teachers who clear a specially designed test for them.

Appointment of Qualified Bureaucrats: It is mainly because of the incompetent bureaucrats in different states that the education mess is persisting in Indian schools. These bureaucrats must be removed from education departments and domain experts should be appointed to handle the school education reformation process.

Service-Level Agreements: Teachers must sign legal Service-Level Agreements (SLAs) to ensure education quality in the schools. They must be prosecuted if they are not able to provide the assured level of education services.

Ban on Private Tuitions: When school teachers are not able to teach properly in government as well as private schools, they ask students to join and pay for private tuition. Action must be taken against teachers who take salaries from schools but promote private tuitions. Private tuitions are not required if school education is good. Students should be informed about the perils of private education.

Outlay for School Education: While the annual outlay for school education should be increased by all Indian states, no money should be allocated for school infrastructure such as buildings, classrooms, etc. because massive government corruption happens under construction projects. Expenditure should only be made on making new curriculums, appointment of qualified teachers, and improvement in the content quality of books.

Education for Jobs: In the existing system, all irrelevant subjects are taught carelessly in schools, but none of these subjects is relevant for employment. Education in each class must target a particular type of job. In other words, the subjects and books must be selected for a particular job that the student intends to get after schooling.

Stop Dirty Politics: In the dirty political system of India, politicians tell blatant lies about their work in the education sector to deceive the voters. Strict restrictions should be imposed on politicians who are making false claims on education quality and they should not be allowed to advertise about the performance of schools in their states. School education is equally bad in the private as well as government schools of all the states.

Impact Analysis: An independent core committee of external experts should be constituted to oversee and ensure the quality of school education on a regular basis. This committee will also analyze the impact of the new education system on the employment levels.

Note: If the education in schools is perfect, the students will be employable just after their schooling. Then they need not attend any college or university for higher education.

The governments in different states of India must take immediate steps to completely discard their obsolete education systems and adopt the new education model as suggested above.

Since most bureaucrats in India are unskilled and governments are slow in their response, parents and students must form groups to launch campaigns in their areas to get the school education systems totally modernized.

The steps for the implementation of the new education model are given below.

STEPS FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF NEW EDUCATION SYSTEM

The following steps should be taken for the implementation of the new school education model.

1. In the initial phase which can be started in a month, each state should identify at least 10 schools where the new model could be used. New schools can also be set up.
2. These schools can be called **भारत के प्रगतिशील स्कूल** or Progressive Schools of India.
3. A few teachers can be selected and trained to teach according to the new model.
4. The bureaucrats and politicians should issue government notifications for states to implement the new system in a fixed timeframe.
5. The Central government can coordinate with different states to get the new system implemented.
6. All the students in existing schools should be immediately given the option to adopt the new system.
7. I can help the governments as well as schools get the new education model thoroughly implemented.

ABOUT THE EDUCATION REPORT AUTHOR (RAKESH RAMAN)

Rakesh Raman is a government's national award-winning [journalist](#) and founder of the humanitarian organization RMN Foundation in New Delhi. Besides working at senior editorial positions with leading media companies, he was writing an exclusive edit-page column regularly for The Financial Express, which is a daily business newspaper of The Indian Express Group.

Nowadays, for the past 12 years, he has been [running](#) his own global news services on multiple news sites. He runs various human rights protection, environment protection, education awareness, and anti-corruption campaigns, and [publishes](#) digital magazines and research reports on different subjects. He runs the Pathway platform, which is a

growth-centric technology program to help [emerging businesses](#) leapfrog in the increasingly competitive global marketplace.

Earlier, he had been associated with the United Nations (UN) through the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) as a digital media expert to help businesses use technology for brand marketing and business development.

He had set up and managed a free school for 5 years during 2015-2019 to impart modern education to deserving children at the J.J. Colony of Dwarka, Sector 3, New Delhi. Among other international technology content projects, he has introduced – “*Raman’s Tech Tale Series – Knowledge Stories for Children,*” a book series aimed to spread [technology awareness](#) among children through short stories and novels.

This work has also found a mention in Bookbird, a journal of international children’s literature, produced by IBBY, the International Board on Books for Young People. He has also written a number of other books for children. He has been running a comprehensive edutainment site named “[RMN Kids](#)” for children, parents, and teachers.

As part of an ongoing education awareness [campaign](#) in Delhi, he - along with the students of his RMN Foundation - had been presenting a street play – चमेली की पढ़ाई – which highlights the problems in the current education ecosystem. In the Modern Alternative Education model, he has [introduced](#) a “*Multiple Subject Guide for Primary Learning.*” Now, he is in the process of developing a free interactive YouTube platform to impart modern education to all types of students, parents, and teachers.

At present, Rakesh is associated with the Varieties of Democracy ([V-Dem](#)) Project as a Country Expert for India to provide expert research inputs on multiple topics pertaining to democracy and governance. The V-Dem Project is managed by V-Dem Institute under the University of Gothenburg, Sweden.

He has also worked as an [editor](#) for Wikipedia, which is a free online global encyclopedia. He has launched a nationwide campaign to introduce social democracy in

India in order to build an egalitarian society in which all citizens could enjoy equal rights, opportunities, freedoms, and access to justice. You can [click here](#) to read his full profile.

Circulation of School Education Report 2025

The School Education Report 2025 has been published by RMN Foundation, which is the humanitarian initiative of RMN News Service. It is being circulated among different UN agencies, government departments, industry associations, leading global politicians, international political organizations, colleges / universities, civil society organizations, social activists, teachers, and others in India and abroad.

As the founder of RMN Foundation and editor of RMN News Service, I have researched and published this report independently without any financial or other support. People and organizations are urged to support this academic initiative aimed to provide better education and career opportunities to all students in India.

Donation Online and with PayPal: Individual donors can [click here](#) to donate online and you can also [click here](#) to pay with PayPal.

Contact

Rakesh Raman

Founder

[RMN Foundation](#)

463, DPS Apts., Plot No. 16, Sector 4

Dwarka, Phase I, New Delhi 110 078, INDIA

WhatsApp / Mobile: 9810319059 | [Contact by email](#)